

IMPROVED APPROACHES TO INCREASING ENERGY EFFICIENCY OF BUILDINGS

Nishonov Kamoliddin Akhrorjon o'g'li

Fergana Polytechnic Institute

2nd year student of the Faculty of Energy

"EEE chair" assistants

Omonullayev Boburjon Ilkhomjon o'g'li

Annotation: This article provides information on how to improve the energy efficiency of buildings. In the field of energy, this is one of the most important issues.

Keywords: Power grid, complex, building, efficiency, technical, heating, insulation, investment, energy saving.

If we talk about a comprehensive approach to solving energy saving problems, it becomes clear that in addition to heat loss, the structure of buildings and heating systems must take into account other aspects. An integrated approach should cover three basic and popular principles of sustainable development: the balance of environmental, economic and social aspects. All three rules should define the criteria for which buildings are evaluated and compared. It turns out that energy consumption is one of the many criteria.

An integrated approach to building energy efficiency in buildings includes additional aspects such as size. -investments, sales analysis, use of environmentally friendly materials, design principles, interior comfort, etc. Now, let's take a closer look at them [1,2].

One of the most important aspects of investment is to make decisions on energy efficiency measures. No energy saving project can be implemented when it is not economically feasible. Expenditures in cities are much higher in rural areas than in rural areas, and there is a difference in price levels during periods of economic growth and economic crisis. The total investment should include architectural design, technical design, construction of the required quality of the

building, including full-scale construction, technical equipment of the building, as well as VAT (VAT).

Analyze the profitability of a building over its life cycle. The energy efficiency of buildings and the economics of the measures taken must be balanced. It is necessary to determine the economically acceptable level by analyzing the profitability of the building, taking into account the entire life cycle of the building. EU program 2010/31 / EC represents the level of energy efficiency "at an economically acceptable level" The lowest price in the calculated economic period. Low capital is determined by capital. Costs, maintenance and operating costs (energy and capital costs, energy input), if any, and waste disposal will be incurred where available.

Complex housing planning. The most important aspects of integrated planning are: Use of data from installers and manufacturers of energy-saving systems Mathematical modeling of buildings as a single energy system and determination of heat consumption over time Analysis of the results of the application of analogues of energy-saving solutions 30 -o themselves: their compactness, including the availability of shortcuts to up and down traffic areas or workplaces; short distance on public transport; social balance to be achieved - a sustainable quality of life; introduction of compact types of buildings to minimize heat loss; -use of maximum natural light; maximum use of solar energy for passive heating, providing access to the district heating system; minimizing damage to the environment [2].

Comfortable climate in the buildings. Every building needs to be designed and built in a healthy, safe and comfortable indoor climate. The construction plan and clear technical plans must meet the climatic requirements for the buildings specified in national legislation. The condition of the building should be taken into account when planning how to retain heat. Buildings should be designed and constructed in such a way that the indoor air is free of water vapor is concentrated in the buildings (windows, frames, walls, ventilation systems, etc.) and does not

cause damage. Humidity in the room remains within the specified values. Rules and guidelines, sound absorption measures should be followed. The concentration of volatile organic compounds (VOC) in the design and construction of buildings shall be taken into account and minimized in accordance with the requirements of national legislation. In addition, it is necessary to take into account the concentration of radon and, if necessary, take special measures to reduce it or meet the requirements of national regulations [3].

Ecological materials. Building materials are part of the evaluation of a building and are critical to evaluating all building systems. In the European Union, everything must have a label for building materials. Indicates that the materials will be used and distributed in EU countries, as well as tested and that the materials meet all 31 requirements. However, this label does not mean that the material is environmentally harmful or environmentally harmful. According to the CAPEM project, eco-material is a material product that has a negative impact on the environment and health. For example, when reconstructing or modernizing a building, care should be taken to use or replace materials that contain the following harmful substances: asbestos, freons; cadmium-containing substances (eg dyes); solvents, plastics or substances containing formaldehyde, resins; Uncertified wood, adhesives and bitumen, tropical wood paints, except as approved by the Forestry Council. There are several basic design principles used in the design of energy-efficient buildings: compactness of the building, optimal zoning and location, use of sunlight, natural light, shade and heat protection .. If the technical application of the construction project is incorrect, even the best planning is useless. There is a need for monitoring and inspection during the construction operation planning, design and construction completion phases. The quality control process is evaluated as an assessment of project implementation. Usually the project is approved in accordance with the requirements of national legislation. Subsequent monitoring (on a regular basis) is carried out throughout the construction process. All construction processes must be inspected and measured.

It is estimated that the total heat loss through the roof surface can be about 10-20%. Regardless of the climatic conditions, it is recommended to use insulating roofing material with a thickness of at least 15-20 cm (thermal conductivity $\lambda = 0.040 \text{ W / mK}$). In a Central European climate, 30 cm of insulation is required for houses that consume less energy than 40 cm for a passive house. Background insulation. The walls of many homes are the largest source of energy loss and have the greatest impact on energy consumption. Walls can account for about 20-30 percent of total heat loss. Regardless of the climatic conditions, it is recommended that the minimum external insulation of the walls be less than 10 cm ($\lambda = 0.040 \text{ W / mK}$). The average is 24 cm for energy-efficient homes and 35 cm for passive homes in Central Europe. Coefficient of heat transfer of windows 33. In addition to receiving sunlight, windows account for about 15% of total heat loss through heat transfer. The amount of heat energy lost depends mainly on the number of windows and the thickness of the frame, as well as the degree to which the window is filled with foam. The energy quality of windows is the heat transfer coefficient (U-value). The value of all windows (UW) includes the glass U-value, the frames and the loss through the thermal bridge across the glass coating. Basically, old windows with a UW of about 5.6 V / K have a single frame. The two squares and the exterior glass had a UW value of up to 2.3 W / C . At a modern three-bottle depth, the UW value can reach $0.8 \text{ W / m}^2\text{S}$.¹³ The stickiness of the building. Heat loss is the flow of heat from the inside of a building to the outside environment inside the building.

In short, the installation of thermometers increases the energy consumption awareness of individual heating and cooling devices. Use of renewable energy sources. Limited reserves of fossil energy sources, environmental problems and the expected increase in energy demand are one of the main reasons for the more active development of renewable energy sources. Renewable energy sources are energy from natural resources such as water, sunlight, wind, rain, waves, geothermal sources, and biomass to generate electricity and heat. The availability of renewable

energy depends on a number of factors, including the level of technological development and costs. These factors should always be considered.

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